

Effects of incorporating learner corpus data into EAP writing materials development:
L1 Chinese students' awareness of the use of epistemic lexical verbs in L2 English
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Since the mid-1980s, there has been an increased interest in using corpus data to develop EAP teaching/learning materials. However, most researchers and materials developers mainly relied on native English-speaker corpora, and learner corpora still remained marginal. Nesselhauf (2004) argue that, for language learning, it is not only important to know what typical native language is, but what typical difficulties learners have. To achieve this purpose, the present study explored the value of learner corpora in EAP writing materials development in helping learners to increase their knowledge of epistemic lexical verbs (ELVs).

Firstly, a L1 English corpus and L1 Chinese learner corpus of English consisting of MA academic essays were compiled and compared the use of ELVs. After, two types of learning materials were developed: the first included data from L1 English corpus, the second added both L1 Chinese learner corpus data and prior corpus findings. These two materials were transferred to Qualtrics and allocated to the control group (CG) and experimental group (EG) of MA L1 Chinese students respectively. Their performance was assessed at the pre-, post-, and delayed post-tests; their processing time on each test and their IELTS overall score were used as dependent variables to test their relative effectiveness on learning performance. The quantitative findings were triangulated with data collected via questionnaire and semi-structured interview to examine learners' attitudes regarding incorporating learner corpus data in materials development.

A mixed-effects regression model showed that both EG and CG demonstrated a higher accuracy at post- and delayed post-test compared to pre-test. Also, both groups' learning performance increased at a rate of 0.10 IELTS overall score. However, no significant difference was identified between two groups at any three testing points. The qualitative data suggest over 85% students in both groups preferred to see learner corpus data and believed it would better to address their own problematic usage.

References

Nesselhauf, N. (2004). Learner corpora and their potential for language teaching. In J.M. Sinclair (Eds.), *How to use corpora in language teaching* (pp.125-156). John Benjamins Publishing Company.